

Between the Search for the Absolute and Psychopathology: Does Spirituality Help in Healing? A Phenomenological Reading.¹

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Incipit

*God will not die on the day we no longer believe in a personal deity,
but we will die on the day our lives are no longer filled
with the splendour of the ever-renewed miracle,
whose sources are beyond all reason.*

Dag Hammarskjöld²

From the very beginning, human beings have experienced anxieties and restlessness. Since then, their imagination has urged them to dare, their intelligence to reflect, and their spirit to wander beyond the stars toward that dimension in which space ceases to be space, time ceases to be time, and the *mysterium* reveals itself in all its power.

This represents a profound inner need, an eloquent response to the human demand for spirituality and elevation, expressed by a humanity striving to rethink the world in order to recover its soul. If ours is indeed the *dürftige Zeit* (destitute time) described by Martin Heidegger, then the inescapable necessity of posing the question of the meaning of being emerges with renewed force. This entails a return to that fundamental question whose radical nature, when

¹ The title of the original paper in Italian read: *Tra ricerca dell'assoluto e psicopatologia: la spiritualità aiuta a guarire? Una lettura fenomenologica.*

² Dag Hammarskjöld, *Tracce di cammino*, ed. G. Dotti, tr. E. Östgren (Biella: Qiqajon, 2006), 85.

it truly touches us, involves us so deeply that it sets us upon the path of salvation, following the trace of that mystery which discursive thought tends to forget and conceal.

Introduction

The onset of illness seems to inaugurate a new and original relationship with being, with things, and with the human person himself: a letting-be that opens onto mystery. This makes it possible for thought to approach that part of our being that both grounds and transcends us. It involves approaching the limit of logical thought, a limit that disposes existence toward an authentic openness, rediscovering within mystery its own destiny which, in the silence of words, opens space to the spiritual moment, which may be described as that primordial intimacy that has been lost, an intimacy that consists in proximity and abandonment, listening and waiting. In its depth, spirituality appears as something that predisposes us, yet something over which we cannot exercise control.

Here one experiences a time in which instant and duration merge, allowing human beings to dwell upon the threshold of mystery, a place of uncertain boundaries, sometimes obscure and even perilous. The threshold may be inhabited and perhaps even guided, but it can never truly be possessed.

Only in this way can that light of *Nada* (Nothingness), which illuminates the Absent and reconciles the self with itself, allow us to rediscover the horizon of a possible meaning of life opened toward truth. This truth hides within every self and every story; it is the voice of the infinite that generates words capable of expressing profound meaning.

When a situation finally becomes expressible, the language that emerges often resembles that of ancient prayer. At this limit, it is appropriate to pause and fall silent, allowing the word to yield to the absolute silence of the ineffable infinite, capable of entering the most hidden folds of interiority, up to the threshold of mystery.

Questions of Meaning and the Ineffable Absolute of Mystery

*There is a time in life when man's questions become more radical,
more essential.*

Graziano Martignoni³

Reflecting on why most human beings expect the end of the world, Immanuel Kant wrote, in *The End of All Things*, that such a conviction arises:

in the fact that reason says to them that the duration of the world has worth only insofar as the rational beings in it conform to the final end of their existence; if, however, this is not supposed to be achieved, then creation itself appears purposeless to them, like a play having no resolution and affording no cognition of any rational aim.⁴

The secularised and individualistic culture of efficiency appears to dominate our age. Technology and scientific research are still strongly valued and are too often conceived in opposition to a sapiential form of knowledge, a knowledge that involves the whole of human existence and cannot be reduced merely to the provision of technical instruments. Medicine has thus increasingly developed within a cultural horizon of unlimited progress and absolute freedom, aimed at overcoming every biological and social limit, in pursuit of a world without pain, death, or evil. Health and salvation have almost become synonymous. Yet, since it is impossible to escape human limitation, individuals often place their trust in symbols of immortality upon which to ground their security and their purpose in life.

It becomes important, then, to know how to orient oneself and choose to rely on Someone or something that will not disappoint expectations because within the human being, as *cor inquietum* (a restless heart), there burns a continuous search for meaning and a strong exploratory feeling of the abyss.

Illness is fundamentally and universally a possibility that affects us all. It is a possibility that affects every human being, prior to any possible distinction between those who care and those who are cared for. Illness involves a radical

3 Graziano Martignoni, "Nella stagione degli addii: Terre di ghiaccio, terre di fuoco e terre di vento," *Sentieri nelle Medical Humanities*, 28 November 2024, <https://www.rivista-smh.ch/articolo/nella-stagione-degli-addii/>

4 Immanuel Kant, "The end of all things," in *Religion and Rational Theology*, tr. and ed. Allen W. Wood and George Di Giovanni (Cambridge University Press, 1996), 217–232, 224.

transformation of the person, both in the representation of one's own existence and in the multiple dimensions of lived experience.

Spirituality helps to restore balance because everything comes to be viewed in the light of meaning, allowing the contingency of an event to be transformed into the outline of a destiny. When illness strikes, a profound metamorphosis occurs in the person's way of representing and interpreting his or her existence, as well as in the innumerable dimensions of life.

Spirituality helps us to find balance and perhaps even to reconcile ourselves with things, because everything is read and interpreted in the perspective and dynamics of meaning, the only thing that can perhaps transform the contingency of the event into the design of a destiny and a destination.

From this arises an indescribable intuition that goes beyond immediate experience and suggests that human finitude is not abandoned to itself but may be destined to reunite with an immanent totality. This intuition constitutes the most direct and immediate testimony to the possibility of that ecstatic rapture described by Richard of Saint Victor, who spoke of "the phenomenology of inner vision and the *excessus mentis*, the exercise of free will in relation to the education of the affections and passions, and Love as the cornerstone of the very organisation of the cosmos."⁵

The Art of Medicine

The most calamitous and frail of all creatures is man, and equally the proudest.

Michel de Montaigne⁶

Within our culture, within which modern medicine itself has developed, death almost always becomes part of fundamental questions concerning the origins and purposes of life, the existence of an immortal soul, and a life that seldom gives these issues adequate consideration, even though they remain at the margins of consciousness and tend to emerge in particular circumstances: the death of significant persons, serious illnesses with potentially fatal outcomes, or painful events in general.

5 Mira Mocan, *L'arca della mente. Riccardo di San Vittore nella Commedia di Dante* (Firenze: Leo. S. Olschki, 2012), xix.

6 Michel de Montaigne, *Essais*, bk II, chap. 12, in *Œuvres complètes*, ed. Albert Thibaudet and Maurice Rat (Paris: Gallimard, 1962), 429.

For this reason, it has become increasingly necessary to continue educating healthcare professionals in the relational and communicative aspects that characterise a more intersubjective and humanised approach to medicine. This need arises especially within a medical context that is becoming increasingly technological, where diagnostic and therapeutic interventions are often marked by growing technical specialisation, particularly in hospital settings. Attentive and compassionate listening, empathetic communication, and the ability to shift one's perspective in order to place oneself in the position of patients, and sometimes of their families, thus become fundamental for all healthcare professionals and represent a precious time within the process of care. The humanisation of medicine, therefore, must begin with listening to patients' life stories, narratives into which every practitioner should attempt to enter not only professionally but also with kindness and humble respect.

Historically, there are reasons why religious and spiritual questions have often been neglected within a demanding medicine that aspires to abandon the irrational in favour of the rational. Psychiatry, however, has gradually emerged from the constraints of its historical origins and from the empiricism associated with the particular nature of mental illness. It is a discipline that considers the human being in his or her entirety: biological, psychological, emotional, and intellectual, but also, at least in some sense, spiritual. This dimension generates processes that influence psychic life and must therefore be taken into account in treatment.

In patients with psychiatric disorders, however, spirituality has often been regarded as a potentially aggravating factor, capable of reinforcing delusions, generating moral guilt, and provoking existential questioning.

Spirituality and religion

Here my high imagination failed me; but already my desire and my will were turning, like a wheel revolving uniformly by the love that moves the sun and the other stars.

Dante Alighieri, Paradise (Canto 33)

It is important to distinguish spirituality from religion. Spirituality refers to a relationship with transcendence and may be considered an attribute of individuals. Religion, by contrast, is an organised social entity. Unlike religion, spirituality is difficult to define. Today, religions appear to function less as systems of truths to be believed and more as reservoirs of meaning that are

consulted during difficult and crucial moments of existence. This problem of giving meaning to one's suffering, parallel to that of the meaning of life, animates and perhaps unsettles contemporary thought.

Today, spiritual life clearly bears the mark of personal demand, giving rise to a new requirement: the tendency to consider religious ideas true primarily because they have been chosen as personally meaningful. This development partly stems from the evolution of individual consciences, which have become increasingly individualised, and partly from an unprecedented historical situation in which diverse cultures encounter one another as never before.

The term spirituality has become more widely used in our time than the term religion. Like personality and health, it is a complex concept. It cannot be defined through a simple continuum but must instead be understood as multidimensional.

Religion is characterised by boundaries and limits, whereas spirituality is defined precisely by the difficulty of establishing such boundaries. Spirituality does not necessarily imply religion, and each person defines spirituality differently.

One may speak of a spiritual experience during moments such as contemplating nature, walking in the mountains, or other forms of reflection. Across different definitions of spirituality, several core elements recur: beliefs, values, the meaning and purpose of life, the notion of transcendence, and the idea of connection, whether with the universe, a higher power, a community, or even the material world.

Spiritual experience may be approached through different practices such as meditation, prayer, art, literature, or poetry. Many individuals today describe themselves as spiritual but not religious. Some non-believers express a form of secular spirituality, such as, for example, Slavoj Žižek, who regard spirituality as an individual and secular notion.

This widespread contemporary understanding of spirituality differs from its original meaning. Some thinkers defend a spirituality without God, without dogma, and without Church, an atheistic spirituality that would guard against both fanaticism and nihilism. From this perspective, the religious attitude would not concern devotion to a transcendent deity but rather the finite human relationship with the infinite, our temporal experience of eternity, and our relative access to the absolute and to mystery. In this sense, "the knowledge that what is inaccessible to us truly exists, manifesting itself as the greatest wisdom

and beauty that our limited faculties can grasp only in their most primitive form, this knowledge, this feeling, lies at the centre of true religiosity.”

The aspects of human life that are linked to experiences transcending sensory phenomena are often described as spiritual. Even when a religious element is present, the spiritual dimension of human life is frequently associated with the meaning and purpose of existence.

According to Harold Koenig, religion is an organised system of beliefs, practices, rituals, and symbols that designate the sacred (God, a higher power, ultimate truth). This system defines relationships with others and establishes the responsibilities of each individual within a community.

Spirituality, by contrast, represents a personal response through which individuals seek to address questions about the meaning of life and self-acceptance, including relationships with oneself, others, and the universe. It involves the search for meaning, the relationship with the sacred, and the experience of transcendence.

Religion and religiosity are therefore neither necessary nor sufficient conditions for defining spirituality today, and one may affirm that every person possesses a spiritual dimension, whether or not they belong to a religious tradition.

Spirituality

The world reveals itself through the language that names it.

David Le Breton

The concept of spirituality enjoys widespread popularity, even though attempts to reach a general consensus on its nature have repeatedly failed.⁷ According to the *Oxford English Dictionary*, spirituality refers to “the quality or condition of being spiritual,” while the term spiritual refers to “that which concerns... the spirit.” The spirit, in turn, may be understood as the vital principle in human beings, their essential nature or character, and a particular disposition or inclination of the mind that characterises individuals.⁸

7 See J. Dyson, M. Cobb, B. Forman, “The meaning of spirituality: a literature review,” *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 26, no. 6 (1997): 1183–1188.

8 See J. A. Simpson and E. S. C. Weiner, eds., *The Oxford English Dictionary*, 2nd ed., vol. 16 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1989), 251–259.

Spirituality can evoke a response of adherence only if contemporary human beings abandon the presumption of Promethean reason and, in descending to the roots of human experience, once again become courageous and humble seekers of hope, humility, and truth.

Illness and its manifestations belong to the phenomenology of a changing world, rather than to that of stability. It is part of the *condition humaine*, in which identity oscillates between the risk of dispersion and the creation of new configurations. To experience illness means inhabiting the frontier, the limit, and the threshold, a fragile resting place for personal identity, while at the same time remaining open to the other, to alterity and alienness that are present in every human being. In this condition of “frontier,” one describes the unstable and restless passage between intimacy and extimacy, between inside and outside, between the self and the other, between the body and the world, an experience that our transitional age attempts to represent.

The etymological definition of spirituality is rarely used today. In a broad sense, spirituality may function as a resource or therapeutic means, but it may also, at times, become a source of disturbance. In the definition proposed by the World Health Organisation’s Quality of Life working group in 1995, spirituality was described as “the perception that individuals have of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns.”⁹ To this day, however, no universally accepted definition has been reached within the scientific community, despite the concept appearing intuitively understandable.

The word spiritual derives from the Latin *spiritus*, meaning breath: the vital breath, the principle of life, the essence of life itself. It refers to questions of meaning and values, to that which connects the person with the world and guides them beyond the merely physical, social, and psychosocial dimensions of human existence.

While maintaining an operational distinction between the therapeutic and spiritual domains, each with its own proper field of competence, it is nevertheless important to bring these approaches into dialogue, grounded in the complementarity of their respective dynamics.¹⁰ Otherwise, there is a risk

9 World Health Organization, “The World Health Organization Quality of Life Assessment (WHOQOL): Position Paper from the World Health Organization,” *Social Science & Medicine* 41, no. 10 (1995): 1403–1409, 1405.

10 See B. Ugeux, *Retrouver la source intérieure* (Paris: Éditions de l’Atelier, 2000).

of confusion regarding the boundaries between disciplines and of diminishing the specific aims of both medicine and spirituality.

To adopt a holistic approach to health and to promote spiritual care aligns with the very nature of medicine, which is rooted in service and compassion, two profoundly spiritual values.

Faced with a scientific medicine often guided by a logic of technical power and mastery, taking spirituality into account allows medicine to remain anchored in reality, to accept the real, especially in its vulnerability, its finitude, and in what cannot be resolved or repaired.¹¹

Perhaps the challenge of contemporary medicine is precisely to open itself to the spiritual dimension and to accept the assistance of spirituality in confronting the profound questions raised by fragility, finitude, and human powerlessness in the face of excessive suffering. In the end, the response to these questions of meaning may come not so much from science as from spirituality.

The Place of Care

It is said that Hyginus, a mythographer from the early centuries CE, wrote an ancient fable describing the birth of Care. This fable speaks to the suffering and depth contained in the word care. Care is what must preserve life as it exists; it must accompany life for as long as it is present, or better still, care must be a kind of perennial concern for the human being, though not primarily in the sense of biological life, nor merely in relation to psychic health (which others take care of), but in relation to the very existence of the human being.

In this sense, Care becomes the companion of existence, the one who, through her curatorial work, is called to welcome each of us along the course of our own lives, especially in situations of instability, where one walks on ground that is uncertain, threatening, devoid of secure boundaries, and lacking definitive refuges. A “spiritual” consideration of the person thus brings us to the problem of the self, self-awareness and self-control, which may be conceived as the “substance” and “essence” of the human person.

¹¹ See M.F. Chan, “Factors affecting nursing staff in practising spiritual care,” *Journal of Clinical Nursing* 19, no. 15–16 (2010): 2128–2136.

The Phenomenologists of the Lost Continent

Consciousness is always consciousness of something.

E. Husserl

The phenomenologists of the “lost continent” described the psyche’s real identity: psychic identity and personal identity. Where there is reality, there is transcendence and the possibility of error. At the level of the pure ego, one can never truly be mistaken. Whoever lies beyond consciousness is still a person, not an id or something else.

The consciousness each person has of oneself at every instant renders only a partial account of the self. This constitutes a categorical illusion found in Freud and also reappearing in cognitivism. Edith Stein is virtually alone in preserving an essential role for the notion of the pure ego and for the distinction between the pure ego and the transcendental ego.

Why does Stein preserve the pure ego? In Husserl, the role of the pure ego enables the transition from a psychology of consciousness (Franz Brentano) and from descriptive phenomenology (the description of lived experiences as such) to transcendental phenomenology, that is, Husserlian phenomenology. Husserl carried out a kind of de-realisation of consciousness. Consciousness is not something contained “in the mind”; rather, consciousness is a mode in which objects are present according to their own manner of manifesting themselves. Consciousness is not a receptacle; it is, instead, a property of interneuronal experience.

Beginning from an experience, each person thematises that experience, thereby bringing to light its intentional structure, and thus the type of act involved. Every interneuronal act has an ego-centred structure: the pure ego is what resists reduction. Once consciousness has been de-realised and reality reduced to essence, what remains is the pure ego. For this reason, every lived experience remains, in some sense, egocentered.

The pure ego also has a further role. The reflective path “à la Descartes” can begin not only from the Cartesian route but also from the direct becoming-aware of the ego. The pure ego is not merely the formal “filling” of a lived experience; it is also the embodiment of an enacted experience, the embodiment of activity. The pure ego functions as the point at which one’s activity is applied in the present. It can be activated at a level that may be, each time, more or less profound. It cannot be said that only a “part” of the person is activated; rather,

it is a point of insertion of the person as such, a point from which the subject takes a stance. Only when the pure ego is lost does it make sense to describe the self as a stream of lived experiences, as a kind of dream. Here we enter the sphere of the loss of the *Meinhaftigkeit* of the pure ego, of the experience “I am purely myself.”

It is through *intentio*, that is, in intentionally directing oneself toward something transcendent with respect to oneself, that a new dimension of life begins for the ego. This is analogous to the psychic development of a child, who, with wonder, becomes aware of reality at the moment of separating from identification and fusion with the maternal figure.

Intentionality also makes spiritual life possible, marked by a new class of lived experiences: the class of apprehensions or acts characterised by a conscious orientation toward an external objectivity. This manifests not merely as a simple succession of data, but as continuous apprehension, an ongoing addition of what follows to what precedes it, a continuity among individual apprehensions, and finally the setting in motion of something absolutely new through the preceding act.

The identification of this “essential nucleus” of the person with “existence” in the sense of Martin Heidegger and Karl Jaspers, an identification carried out by Ludwig Binswanger, offers the advantage of studying human functional unity from its most intimate ontological sources. The current crisis of the medical sciences may also be understood as an attempt to reconstruct a global attention to the human being, capable of restoring the psychophysical and spiritual unity of existence.

The effort to broaden the therapeutic context so that it excludes no health care professional from intervention reflects the possibility of synthesis for those who focus on the human being. Over millennia, there has been a gradual reduction: we have moved from a holistic understanding of the psychophysical unity of the human person toward a narrower focus of interest and, consequently, of healthcare intervention. Perhaps the aim was to bring this information together into scientific systematisations and rigid classificatory schemes.

The Cultural Dimension

The concept of culture has deep and ancient roots, as evidenced by Greek *paideia*. The meaning of the term seems to derive from German historical philosophy. J. G. Herder distinguished between the form in which culture is experienced by the individual and the structure perceived as the collective heritage of a

community. To differentiate these elements, Herder spoke of *Bildung* and *Kultur*. By using the term *Bildung* to describe culture, Herder attributes to it a function that may be understood as imaginative and representational, as suggested by the etymology itself: *Bild* means image. In order to better understand the elements underlying spirituality and mental illness, it is essential to reflect on this dimension of culture and on its representational function. What cultural dimension sustains these circumstances, also called the “limit situations” of existence?

This path, if we consider it carefully, does not appear fundamentally dissimilar from those proposed, each in its own style, by W. Dilthey, H. Bergson, E. Husserl, and M. Heidegger: authors who, in one way or another, directly or indirectly, consciously or not, reconnect with the traditional method of inward spiritual inquiry.

Understood as a rejection of limits, as “being-in-the-world and being-beyond-the-world” (*Über-Welt-hinaus-sein*) in Ludwig Binswanger, or, even more, as Maurice Bellet writes, “as a word of human language inserted into that chain of signification in which the unconscious expresses itself without ever saying so.”¹²

In our time, the crisis of presence can also be understood as a crisis of meanings.

Origin of the term ‘healing’

*“Healing is a matter of time,
but it is sometimes also a matter of the opportune moment.”*

*Hippocrates*¹³

The etymology of the word “healing” derives from the ancient Germanic *warjan*, which in Old High German means “to repair,” “to defend,” “to keep away,” and which in turn refers to the root *var*, from which come *wahren* (“to protect, preserve”) and *bewahren* (“to safeguard, watch over,” or even “to cover”).

Healing refers not only to symptomatic reduction or the removal of causes, but also to a profound meaning within the affective relationship in which the

¹² P. M. Bellet, *Fede e psicanalisi* (Assisi: Cittadella, 1975), 99.

¹³ Hippocrates, *Precepts*, 1, vol. 1, tr. P. Potter, Loeb Classical Library (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2022), 303.

sufferer can feel protected and defended in the face of any event experienced as inevitable.

Conceived initially as an objectifying and positivistic science, modern medicine has largely erased this extraordinary affective bond, leaving “good” primary care and “good” psychiatry to prevail. Nevertheless, contemporary medicine has become unproductive in a negative sense: it shelters, keeps away, and protects society from the sick, rather than protecting the sick from their suffering.

Healing is not only a medical practice but also a social practice: today, moreover, with a meaning diametrically opposed to that found in other cultures and in the past. Science is built upon the incapacity of the sensible to render an account of the truth of things. Roger Bastide reminds us that neither therapy nor healing exists without the possibility of social sharing.¹⁴

Consequently, an additional element must be considered: in order to ensure healing, it is not sufficient to eliminate causes or reduce symptoms; it is also necessary that the patient’s return to the social fabric occur as the return of a “normal” individual. It is clear that the concepts of “normality” and “healing” possess deep historical and anthropological meanings.

What, then, does healing mean in psychiatry? Giovanni Jervis offers a stimulating and lucid account:

In psychiatry, it is not easy to define what recovery means. Apparently, there should be no uncertainty: a person is ill, has disorders, and would like to be well; they cannot cope with certain circumstances in life and want to find the energy and courage to face them again. Other situations may seem just as simple. A man may not consider himself ill, but he talks and shouts to himself, barricades himself in his house and throws stones at his neighbours. The neighbours think they know exactly what it means to cure this person: to subject him

¹⁴ See R. Bastide, *Sociologia delle malattie mentali* (Firenze, La Nuova Italia, 1981); see R. Bastide, *Sociologia e psicanalisi* (Bari: Dedalo, 1972); see R. Bastide, *Sogno, trance e follia* (Milano: Jaca Book, 1976).

to appropriate treatment, to make him behave like them and leave his neighbours in peace.¹⁵

As a result, the central dichotomy in psychiatry no longer appears to be between illness and healing, but between illness and normality, between the abnormal and the normal. In other words, the word “healing” seems to have been absorbed into the concept of “normality.”

To speak of healing in psychopathology thus evokes the possibility of “putting someone in a safe place” and the need to welcome them, following, perhaps, the words of William Shakespeare: “Give sorrow words: the grief that does not speak whispers the o’er-fraught heart and bids it break.”¹⁶

We cannot change our relationship to pain unless we transform it ourselves. Pain has many medical implications, not only physical but also psychological. The Canadian psychiatrist Zindel Segal has shown that mindfulness may have an effect comparable to antidepressant medication in treating anxiety and preventing new depressive episodes.¹⁷

André Malraux once suggested that the twenty-first century would be illuminated by spirituality.¹⁸ Yet spirituality remains an uncertain value. It is an art of living that requires audacity, because it leads us to view institutions, especially those to which we often entrust ourselves, in a counterintuitive way. There is nothing merely hedonistic or reassuring about it; rather, there is always something that continually eludes us, and whose pursuit must be taken up again and again with renewed vigour.

Healing is always, in some sense, self-healing, because it occurs through the patient’s body and mind. The body regains the balance it had lost through cellular regeneration. Treatments assist the patient in this process of self-healing, helping the organism to recover equilibrium. It is therefore advantageous, and indeed necessary, to support the ill body through treatment and medication, even though the psychic dimension, faith, morality, and the relational environment are often important and sometimes decisive factors in the healing process.

15 G. Jervis, *Manuale critico di psichiatria* (Milano: Feltrinelli, 1980), 142.

16 W. Shakespeare, *Macbeth*, Act IV, Scene III (Open Road Integrated Media, 2018).

17 See Sidney Jules Blatt, Zindel V. Segal, *Depression and the Self* (Wiley, 1997).

18 See A. Malraux, *La condizione umana* (Milano: Bompiani, 2018).

It is not always possible to restore physical and mental balance unless the patient truly commits to recovering health, maintains consistent trust in the treatment provided, and, at least for some patients, retains trust in life itself or in a benevolent higher power that helps them.

One cannot treat a person as a machine. Illness reflects the social, emotional, and spiritual characteristics of human beings, and to heal a person it is necessary to take this global reality into account. It is reasonable to suppose that the consumption of anxiolytics and antidepressants will continue to increase unless they are integrated with other perspectives of care in the healing process. Spirituality, prayer, or faith, as an act and not merely as the action of a deity, may, in this sense, be associated with healing.

Healthcare systems have expanded in recent decades through the use of highly advanced technologies. This has significantly improved care, but it has also

The Care of the Soul

Psychiatry ultimately becomes, in the final analysis, metaphysics.

K. Schneider

The term *psychiatry* emerged in the early eighteenth century, at a time when medicine was conceived as Medicine in the broadest sense. Psychiatry is sometimes described as the “third branch” of medicine, and it arose – curiously – within a Romantic milieu, that is, within a strand of medicine that studied mental disturbances while attributing great importance to the passions.

What is striking is that the word *psychiatry* – literally “care of the soul” – developed in parallel with another “care of the soul” practised by Protestant pastors. This pastoral care often focused on young “hysterical” women of the eighteenth-century bourgeoisie. In these cases, pastors attempted to uncover a hidden secret, which frequently involved a passionate love, for example, for a stableman or a neighbour’s son. Pastors observed that the expression of such a secret could have a cathartic effect. This, however, was a religious practice rather than a medical one.

Nineteenth-century Romantic psychiatrists, in effect, wrested a range of juvenile pathologies from a moralistic religious framework, recovering from within them a perceptual element. In reality, it was an attempt to detach a whole series of mental disorders from the exclusively scientific conception

of psychiatry. It is within this scientific atmosphere that psychiatry's own systematic elaboration took shape, that is, the observation of persons with mental illness through a lens that was at once Romantic and Enlightenment-inspired, though employing different instruments. The Enlightenment's theoretical instrument was the classical one of observation and experiment. The Romantic orientation, by contrast, relied on speculation as its theoretical instrument for scientific elaboration. Once a name had been given to a science that seeks to study the soul, the question necessarily arises: what is the object of this science?

The care of the soul is not confined to psychiatry alone. It must take into account the patient's human and spiritual dimension, because everything else is secondary. Two convictions sustain the clinician: (a) an unshakable conviction that the noetic dimension underlies symptoms; and (b) confidence in the human capacity for self-distancing and self-transcendence as a way of overcoming conditioning, restoring to the person his or her uniqueness and three-dimensionality: an ever deeper descent into bottomless depths.

Spirituality: a global dimension

*Grown-ups never understand anything by themselves,
and it is tiresome for children to be always and forever explaining
things to them.*

Antoine de Saint-Exupéry (The Little Prince)

We are often unable to grant our gaze an "other" meaning beyond the "ultimate horizon," and we struggle to find words adequate to the deep need for a renewed enchantment: almost a new dream of the world. As a result, various pseudo-solutions – a mixture of religions, psychotherapies, and esotericisms – are now marketed in the crossroads of spirituality to promise guaranteed effects.

What is needed, instead, is to bring together two worlds that often fail to converse, yet could have much to say and offer one another. According to several epidemiological studies, spirituality today has a positive impact on physical and mental health. Neuroscientific research has suggested, in particular, that meditation and, more recently, prayer can influence brain activity: one may think of temporal lobe activity long considered a "divine zone," decreased activity in the parietal lobe implicated in spatial orientation and distance evaluation, or increased activity in the limbic system associated with emotion and feeling. Yet the practical implications of these findings have remained limited.

What, then, is the role of religion and spirituality in healthcare today? In hospitals, there is a long tradition of chaplains' presence, now often described as spiritual accompaniment in order to avoid polemics and move beyond confessional frameworks. Even though each participant often works independently, these companions have access to patients within clinical services and may involve healthcare professionals in their approach.

Yet spirituality is difficult to introduce into a secular environment. This is why it is crucial to provide a workable definition of spirituality in such a context: it is a natural and universal need, whether religious or non-religious, for connection and meaning. For this reason, spirituality cannot be absent from hospital settings.

Religion and spirituality have always constituted elements of personal and social identity, from prehistoric humanity to contemporary societies. Historical, sociological, and anthropological research has shown that spirituality and religion have consistently contributed to social dynamism and change, sometimes positively (peace, love, and social solidarity) and sometimes negatively (conflicts and religious wars, dogmatism). Human beings cannot escape the influence of the spirituality and religion that surround them and shape their identity and psychosocial development, whether or not they are personally active in these domains. These dimensions define persons and participate in their social and personal expressions, whether through religious practice, spiritual belief, or even atheism. Given the close connection between spirituality, religion, and mental life, the question of how they should be considered in mental healthcare is clinically and therapeutically significant.

The hegemony of medicine

*A sign we are, without interpretation
Painless are we and have almost lost
The language in foreign lands.*

F. Holderlin¹⁹

Many critiques, including from physicians themselves, have highlighted the hegemony of the biomedical paradigm. For example, George Engel proposed

¹⁹ Cited in Rolf J. Goebel, "And the Script Sounds': Literary Hermeneutics and Imaginary Listening," *Humanities* 13, no. 4 (2024): 107.

a more complex view of the patient in his well-known article *The Clinical Application of the Biopsychosocial Model*.²⁰ This biopsychosocial approach altered the practices of medical teams by

The biopsychosocial model is a strategy for approaching the person, which attributes the outcome of illness, as well as health, to the intricate and variable interaction of biological factors (genetic, biochemical, etc.), psychological factors (mood, personality, behaviour, etc.) and social factors (cultural, family, socioeconomic, etc.). The biopsychosocial model contrasts with the biomedical model, which attributes illness primarily to biological factors, such as viruses, genes or somatic abnormalities, which the doctor must identify and correct. The biopsychosocial model is applied to disciplines ranging from medicine to psychology to sociology; its acceptance and prevalence vary across disciplines and cultures... The biopsychosocial model reflects the development of disease through the complex interaction of biological, psychological and social factors. For example, a person may have a genetic predisposition to depression, but social factors, such as extreme stress at work and in family life, and individual psychological factors, such as perfectionist tendencies, must be present to trigger this genetic code for depression. A person may have a genetic predisposition to a disease, but social and cognitive factors, according to the model, must intervene to trigger the disease.²¹

It is no longer possible to speak of a strict division of labor between caring for the body and caring for the soul. Alongside cardiac surgeons and other specialists of modern medicine, healers and alternative therapists of every kind – using plants, magnetism, or simply language – continue to be sought within the heart of a Western society that claims to be disenchanted.

What are patients seeking elsewhere when their pathology is effectively managed by contemporary therapies? Healing cannot be reduced exclusively to the cessation of pathology, the lowering of temperature after a violent fever, or the elimination of tumor cells. In sociology, what a society considers abnormal is defined as pathological; this may concern behaviors as well as illnesses.

20 Ibid.

21 Wikipedia, the Free Encyclopedia, s.v. “Modello biopsicosociale,” accessed April 15, 2025, https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modello_biopsicosociale

Medicine itself functions as an agent of normalization beyond its statistical efficacy, just as certain rituals can appear extravagant or strange.

Depending on the culture, healing may designate both the disappearance of symptoms and the end of illness, the restoration of normal biological values or social behaviour; for some, healing can also mean obtaining reparation and liberation, or emerging from the absurdity of meaninglessness by elaborating meaning.²²

Events, or intuitions, may arise from the irrational, from the deep, a-logical obscurities of the human condition. These are human possibilities that exceed the boundaries of “normality” and “non-normality,” and they can be classified as psychotic or schizophrenic only when they are accompanied by a de-structuring of ego-consciousness.

Once every prejudice and every clinical ideology regarding the constitution of psychiatry is suspended, psychotic experience can no longer be regarded as an anarchic web of “symptoms,” but rather as a representation, as a text and a discourse endowed with meaning, even if that meaning is hidden and at times difficult to grasp through ordinary modes of objective and rational knowledge.

Likewise, mystical experience should not be interpreted as a form of life bound to regression and, ultimately, to failed personal maturation. Instead, it should be treated as a human possibility to be analysed within its *Lebenswelt*, in Husserl’s sense. It is not only mystical experience that is linked to the irrational and to intuition (to the *anti-logos*), but also the psychotic form of life which, as Ludwig Binswanger has shown, can be grasped in its essence only by immersing oneself in the epistemic domain of the irrational and of intuition.

In any case, mystical and psychotic experiences are borderline existences, “limit situations” in Karl Jaspers’ sense. Despite their significant differences, they possess a distinctive phenomenological meaning and are radically original. It is certainly not a calculating reason that enables one to grasp their profound *raison d’être* and their human significance.

At the same time, mental health itself is a broad and nuanced concept. Beyond biological and physiological determinants, cultural, social, and philosophical factors shape mental health, such as the presence of meaning and purpose

22 See J.M. Gueullette, *Le pouvoir de guerir, enjeux anthropologiques, théologiques et éthiques* (Paris: Les éditions du Cerf, 2011).

in life, one's assessment of the quality of life, and the quality of interpersonal relationships.

Illness is too great an event to face alone: this applies to both patient and physician. Stories create strong bonds, transforming experience into understanding and pain into dialogue. Compassionate storytelling brings caregiver and patient closer together, giving voice to lived experience and tending to suffering through the power of words.

Therefore, those who care must also be equipped with cultural tools and able to rely on them, engaging in dialogue with the sciences of the spirit. One should not underestimate the fact that silence, the doorway and path to interiority, brings us into contact with the fear of separation from loved ones or from the sources from which we receive support; with the preoccupation of failing in our life or not achieving our ideals; with the restlessness that comes from recognizing that life is short and always accompanied by the shadow of death and dissolution; and with concern about one's own sinful condition and limitations.

Beyond healing, a powerful need for salvation and faces and gazes that beg for glimmers of light and transcendence emerge. The primary task thus becomes to act as sentinels and custodians of our spirituality, and to allow ourselves to be inhabited by it, in order to keep alive the mystical tension toward the absolute in this *dürftige Zeit*, this empty time, of those who care for the pain, suffering, and existence of others.

Integrating the spiritual dimension into psychiatry means considering human beings in their existential totality, that is, in their physical, psychological, and spiritual dimensions. For many scientists, and within holistic reasoning as well, spirituality is a component of the person. It therefore becomes increasingly incoherent, logically and scientifically, not to include this dimension when engaging with the patient through an approach that aims to be humane and comprehensive, particularly in psychiatry.

Understanding the role of religion and spirituality is thus important for psychiatric practice. Yet formal spiritual education remains lacking. It would be important to consider several aspects to better investigate the interface among spirituality, religion, and psychiatry; for example, personal spiritual attitudes, practical attitudes within transpersonal professional psychiatry, skills, changes in attitudes toward religion and spirituality, and changes in clinical practice. Such work would increase knowledge in the field and refine clinicians'

ability to speak about these matters and respond appropriately to their patients' requests for spirituality.

The phenomenology of spirituality and its relevance for psychiatry highlights the extent to which spirituality and religiosity are present in the feelings of most patients. By considering the patient's spiritual dimension, the treating psychiatrist can convey an important message, namely, that the clinician is interested in the person as a whole, thereby strengthening the therapeutic relationship. This consideration is likely to enhance the therapeutic impact of psychiatric interventions, because spirituality is an inseparable part of the human psyche and an essential link in psychological and social development.

Spirituality may be understood as an essential element in the lives of many patients and as an important means of alleviating suffering, particularly suffering related to psychiatric illness. All of this, of course, must occur with full respect for the patient's convictions, the stage of illness, and the preservation of a durable and effective therapeutic alliance.

-Melancholy and the Petrification of Meaning

Life – that is: continually shedding something that wants to die.

F. Nietzsche²³

At every moment, anguish confronts us with radical questions about the meaning of life and death in their intangible phenomenological and anthropological dimensions: about the despair that comes from the loss of hope. In depression, our subjective perceptions of the world and others change, losing the normal distinctions between light and shadow and plunging into the depths of hopeless nights. In the anguish of depression, we no longer hope to live, in the Pascalian sense of the word, but are immersed in a lived time, an inner time, from which the open scenarios of becoming flee: of transcendence, which takes us beyond the past and present when anguish is not within us and seems to anticipate an open and relaxed future. How can we forget Blaise Pascal's dazzling and immortal words on time and hope in his *Pensées*?

Everyone should study their thoughts. They will find them all centred on the past or the future. We almost never think of the present, and

²³ Friedrich Nietzsche, *The Gay Science with a prelude in rhymes and an appendix of songs*, tr. W. Kaufmann (New York: Vintage Books, Bk. 1, no. 26, 1974), 100.

if we do it is simply to shed some light on the future. The present is never our end. Past and present are our means, only the future is our end. And so we never actually live, though we hope to, and in constantly striving for happiness it is inevitable that we will never achieve it.²⁴

It seems that slowly the 'drive,' the stimulus to do things, is diminishing; everything has to do with will and motor skills; when you ask an individual a question, they show difficulty in understanding and responding, and this is not related to a defect in articulation or neurons, but to psychomotor inhibition, where there is a conflict between motivation and activity (drive and muscle), and this is the characteristic alteration of depression. It is so typical that many have thought that this slowdown is followed by the expression of a mood that is actually reactive to the inhibition. Some say, however, that the fundamental symptom is mood alteration, which in depression is sadness, which we call vital sadness, to differentiate it from all other types of sadness. This argument has therapeutic and pharmacological implications, because if it is believed that the primary alteration is psychomotor, drugs that act on activity will be used, seeking a key that disinhibits the inhibited. If, on the other hand, it is believed that the fundamental alteration concerns mood, appropriate drugs will be used, such as serotonin. So it is not just a theoretical question, but there could be therapeutic implications. In addition, there is a strange phenomenon whereby when antidepressants are used, inhibition improves first and then mood. In fact, when a depressed person begins to improve, the first few days are a very dangerous time, because if they have suicidal thoughts, as long as they are inhibited, they do not have the urge to commit suicide, but when they feel more relaxed in terms of activity, that is, they feel that they can do more because their body supports them more and the idea of suicide is strong, it is easier for them to kill themselves. Therefore, this moment of transition, this levelling between the action on motor skills and the action on mood, shows a fictitious improvement that introduces an element of danger and is the moment when they need to be monitored most closely. Kurt Schneider was a great psychopathologist who, when talking about feelings, mood and affectivity, described the psyche from an emotional-sentimental point of view as being structured in layers. Feelings are states of the ego that indicate how the ego perceives and experiences itself from an emotional perspective.

24 Blaise Pascal, *Pensees and Other Writings*, tr. H. Levi (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1999), 21.

Schneider distinguishes different layers of feelings or emotions, arranged hierarchically from the lowest level, closest to the body, to progressively higher levels. The lowest level consists of what he calls feeling-sensations (*Empfindungsgefühle*). This first layer includes all states of the self that correspond directly to a sensation; in other words, the affective component is linked to specific sensory experiences, such as tactile, painful, thermal, or similar sensations. These feelings are closely tied to the sensation itself and tend to last approximately as long as the sensation, or slightly longer depending on the intensity of the stimulus. They are localised in the body and characterised by a precise bodily localisation.

The second layer consists of somatic or vital feelings. These are related to the general condition of the body and are experienced by the self as states of its own bodily existence. They are termed *somatic* or *vital* feelings because they pertain not merely to existence in an abstract sense but to the concrete, psycho-organic experience of life. Unlike sensory feelings, they are diffuse, variable, and difficult to localise precisely. They are typically visceral in nature, associated with cenesthesia (the global bodily sense of well-being or malaise), and often experienced at a visceral level. The sadness characteristic of endogenous depression belongs to this domain. It is a profound psychic sadness that is nevertheless experienced somatically. In this case, there is neither a secondary somatic accompaniment to the symptom nor a somatisation of a psychological state; rather, the sadness is itself somatic. It is a deep form of sadness inseparable from a pervasive state of malaise. In fact, no patient with endogenous depression does not experience a profound sense of bodily distress that is simultaneously psychological and psychosomatic. In this context, the term *vital* refers precisely to this phenomenon: a sadness arising from an alteration of the somatic or vital feelings.

The third layer consists of psychological feelings, while the fourth comprises spiritual feelings. As one moves upward through these levels, one progressively distances oneself from the body and approaches the sphere of the spirit.

A person who is psychomotorically inhibited, whose activity and initiative are markedly reduced, and who experiences a deep and pervasive sadness intertwined with a severe sense of malaise will inevitably develop a particular style of thinking. The themes characteristic of this type of ideation are holothymic, that is, entirely determined by the prevailing mood. Consequently, the thoughts that emerge are predominantly negative and pessimistic. What is characteristic of endogenous depression, however, is that these themes are fixed

and recurrent. They revolve around the devaluation of the self (“I am worthless”), economic ruin (“I possess nothing anymore”), guilt, and hypochondriacal concerns (the loss of health).

For this reason they have been described as themes of loss (*Verlustthemen*). The depressed person experiences life under the sign of the loss of four essential dimensions: self-esteem and self-mastery, personal possessions, bodily integrity, and health. These are objects of loss that may be considered fundamental in human development, representing some of the earliest acquisitions of the developing child. In this sense, depression can be understood as a profound loss, a severe form of mourning, as has often been emphasised. At this stage, however, delusion has not yet emerged.

The first step toward endogenous depression is doubt: the suspicion that something is wrong. Gradually, doubts begin to insinuate themselves into the mind. They become more than mere doubts; they acquire an obsessive quality, becoming anancastic, recurrent, intrusive, and parasitic thoughts that progressively occupy increasing space within the person’s mental life. However, the process does not stop at the level of obsessiveness. If the condition progresses, the individual gradually shifts from doubt to certainty. At this stage, the person’s reality judgment becomes altered, and the process gradually evolves toward delusion.

In depression, delusional ideas tend to revolve around a limited set of recurring themes: delusions of self-devaluation, delusions of guilt, delusions of ruin, and hypochondriacal delusions (what earlier psychiatric traditions referred to as *hypochondria major sine materia*).

The theme of guilt is particularly significant. In fact, what is involved is not merely a belief but a profound feeling of guilt. There is an important difference between how guilt is experienced in depression and how it is ordinarily understood. In everyday moral life, guilt arises from violating a rule, and society responds by imposing punishment. The depressed person, however, experiences guilt as irreparable and unredeemable, which is precisely why the condition is characterised by profound despair.

In extreme cases, the individual may even come to believe that they are immortal, in the sense that death itself becomes impossible. The person feels that the wrongdoing committed is so grave that they must continue living indefinitely, condemned to endure life eternally on earth. In this way, life itself becomes experienced as a form of hell.

All of this occurs within the context of a profound disturbance in the structure of lived experience, particularly in the experience of temporality. From a phenomenological perspective, time is ordinarily articulated into past, present, and future, which correspond to three fundamental psychological attitudes: the present moment of experience, the retention of what has occurred, and the non-prediction of what is yet to come.

In depression, however, this temporal structure becomes profoundly disrupted. The present becomes blocked, and the psychological attitude of projection toward the future ceases to function. Consequently, the present not only loses its orientation toward future possibilities but also becomes saturated with elements of the past. Rather than processing new events as they occur, the present becomes dominated by the rumination of past experiences. For this reason, depressive themes often take the form of silent lamentations, since they concern past elements that intrude into the present. The depressed individual structures the past as though it were present; yet a present structured entirely by the past cannot truly function as a present, precisely because it lacks orientation toward the future. As a result, the depressed person becomes trapped in an anancastic and unproductive cycle of complaint, endlessly revolving around a present that is saturated with the past.

From a phenomenological standpoint, an especially dangerous moment occurs when the depressed individual no longer finds material even for these obsessive themes. When the person becomes incapable of generating or elaborating further themes within this past-dominated present, thought itself comes to a standstill. In such circumstances, suicide may occur: the inability to continue thematising experience within a present filled with the past can ultimately lead to self-destruction.

Desire and will in melancholy

*In magno silentio cordis.*²⁵

It is necessary to reflect on what desire and will mean in the melancholic individual, within this complex mixture of fear and sadness. One may also refer to what Jules Cotard called *immortalité mélancolique* (“melancholic

²⁵ The phrase comes from the tradition of Christian contemplative and monastic spirituality. Expressions about the “silence of the heart” appear throughout medieval and patristic spiritual literature, reflecting the belief that deep inner stillness is the place where one encounters the divine.

immortality”),²⁶ a phenomenon observed in the delusion of negation. Cotard describes the cognitive attitude of patients who declare themselves incapable of performing actions; they feel as though they are already dead, yet at the same time, they experience a form of immortality.

The delusion of negation is thus accompanied by a delusion of immortality. The negation of the senses is intrinsically linked to an affirmation of one’s own body, expressed in the idea of *no longer being able to die*. This is not a joyful immortality but a painful one: the individual is unable to reach any boundary of life, and death itself becomes inscribed within life.

Melancholy may therefore be understood as *acedia* (sloth, apathy), a lack of courage in enduring suffering, and as *instabilitas* (instability), *inquietudine* (restlessness or inner agitation). Melancholy situates the individual within an infinite and unhappy waiting, a form of time that extends indefinitely and lacks the limit that death ordinarily provides. What action could possibly fill such an infinite time? Action itself requires limits to have meaning. In this condition, death is not experienced as the end of suffering; rather, when it appears, it delivers the individual even more profoundly into suffering. The anguish of the melancholic consists in experiencing, all at once, the impossibility of life. This represents a paradoxical negotiation with the notion of limit: the melancholic feels “infinitely limited.”

In this sense, the melancholic seems to encounter limits in every aspect of the world and is therefore inclined to negate it. Melancholy thus becomes a condition characterised by the persistent presence of a hope that is constantly deferred. It is *Verzweiflung* (despair), but not *Hoffnungslosigkeit* (complete hopelessness): the melancholic is desperate, yet not entirely without hope.

Sigmund Freud would later suggest that the melancholic may look at truth with greater clarity than others. At the same time, it is important to recognise that one should neither psychologize the spiritual nor spiritualize the psychological. Depression requires specific and appropriate treatment, particularly because the risk of suicide is real. Psychological work, psychotherapy, and the use of antidepressant medication are

Because such phrases circulated as devotional mottos and paraphrases, they are often difficult to attribute to a single original author.

26 See J. Clair, *L’immortalité mélancolique* (Paris: Éditions Gallimard, 2005).

The Desire for Mystery and Spirituality

*“We shall not cease from exploration
And the end of all our exploring
Will be to arrive where we started
And know the place for the first time.”*

T.S. Eliot²⁷

It is at this point that the desire for mystery and spirituality begins to emerge. In our longing for infinite things, we discover the capacity to be infinite ourselves. Spirituality constitutes an important dimension of life and is no less important for understanding what occurs when it weakens or becomes arid in certain psychopathological experiences. In this sense, spirituality represents a radical dimension of psychiatric care.

No cure is possible unless hope lives within us as an inner attitude that only spirituality can provide, as an openness to mystery, and as a listening for and anticipation of the infinite. Without hope, no cure is possible. Spirituality must therefore accompany and guide us both in everyday life and in the various forms of psychiatric treatment, much like the morning stars that may be contemplated as a place where one can express one's hope.

One may also consider certain aspects of depressive psychodynamics, not only depression as a clinical entity, but also what may be termed the depressive effect. André Haynal defines this as the sensation of a continuous and tireless recommencement, as though one were pervaded by a persistent sense of inadequacy arising from the comparison between what one desires to possess and to be, and what one has actually become and what one has lost.²⁸

Psychoanalysis, phenomenology, anthropoanalysis, and other approaches have expanded the horizons of psychiatry. They have made it more flexible and dynamic, freeing it from an often overly rigid nosographic systematisation. At the same time, they have encouraged psychiatry to take into account not only hereditary and endogenous factors within the internal environment, but also the psychic factors and influences arising from the external world, particularly the human world.

27 T. S. Eliot, “Little Gidding,” V, in *Four Quartets* (London: Faber & Faber, 1959), 59.

28 See A. Haynal, *Il senso della disperazione: la problematica della depressione nella teoria psicoanalitica* (Milano: Feltrinelli, 1980).

Within the melancholic world, the emerging variable is a desperate longing for reciprocal love, unconscious yet vibrantly present in the person's waking awareness. What torments the melancholic is the sense of being unable to attain this reciprocity, unable to act upon it, and the awareness, arising from an undeniable comparison with others, that there exists something which he pursues but which is denied to him. This variable constitutes both his fundamental condemnation and his profound solitude.

He feels the limits of his own existence yet cannot understand how to overcome them. When overwhelmed by suffering and perceiving his existential space becoming increasingly constricted, he turns with longing toward the past, which alone exerts an attraction for him. And yet his presence remains indispensable and precious, because he is, in a certain sense, "more than others," transcending the mere notion of happiness through the depth of his proximity.

The historical evolution of the concept of melancholy leads us to recognise that it cannot be reduced to a single alteration in a single psychic function. Rather, it represents a modification of the entire personality in the multiplicity of its expressions. One begins with thinking itself and eventually recognises that the very nature of thinking requires the acknowledgement of its own impotence. This recognition preserves the otherness and the sacredness of being, giving rise to the inquietude that thought may experience when it finds itself entrusted to a form of being that is given to it in a reciprocity that excludes every illusion of possession.

It is in Heidegger that we can glimpse the possibility of gathering ourselves in contemplation, where he seems to conclude that listening constitutes the essence of language:

The desire to know and the avid demand for explanations do not lead to thoughtful questioning... The desire to know does not want us to listen to what is worthy of being thought about... The fundamental trait of thinking is not questioning, but listening to what is suggested by what must be problematised.²⁹

The centrality of the hermeneutic problem, in particular the hermeneutic problem of psychiatric listening, can only be achieved by renouncing and withdrawing from any claim to possession.

29 M. Heidegger, *In cammino verso il linguaggio* (Milano: Mursia, 1973), 92 e 139.

Conclusion

There is nothing like history for rediscovering the meaning and importance of our presence in the world. History, especially our own history, the one we tell ourselves and others, opens up the distance of time, creating a space and a breath through which we can reflect on what has remained constant and what has changed. To situate oneself within historical time means granting oneself a time of rest, moments in which time itself can slow and settle. Our own era, deeply entangled in the urgency of current affairs, is fundamentally in need of this.

I borrow the words of Wilfred Bion to conclude these reflections:

As I became more able to silence my prejudices, I realised that I was able to grasp the evidence that was there, rather than complaining about the evidence that was not there. As my ears became more accustomed to silence, small sounds became easier to hear... I learned to consider the importance of silence in order to hear the 'weakest sounds.' It worked. And I began to hear sounds that previously would have gone unnoticed.³⁰

Often, through anguish, which creates silence, the person can rediscover the expansion of inner space and the proximity that emerges from distance. This requires becoming *humilis*, a term derived from *humus*, meaning soil or earth. In its literal sense, the word signifies something low, and by extension, something without value, minimal, or insignificant. Yet one must not forget that *humilis* is also the most important adjective used to designate the Incarnation.³¹

Thought discovers itself and experiences its own true nature only where it encounters its own impotence and limitation. It does so where it enters into a genuine encounter with that being which Antonio Rosmini had already addressed in his remarkable work. For Rosmini, the word *being* is the word through which the sacred manifests itself as a concept. It is precisely the word *being* that enables human beings to enter into relation with the divine and to grasp something of the mystery.

³⁰ W. F. Bion, *Il cambiamento catastrofico* (Torino: Loescher, 1981), 65.

³¹ See E. Auerbach, *Le Haut Language. Language litteraire et public dans l' Antiquité tardive et Moyen Age* (Paris: Belin, 2004), 41–42.

“When the spiritual desire that constitutes us – making us ‘other’ – is forgotten, we are reduced to the banal biological destiny in which the only future of birth is death.”³²

Perhaps, when seen from this perspective, spirituality may be understood as a ray of sunlight gently entering the room of a dying person!

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